

PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF FORMING STUDENTS' BEHAVIOR BASED ON SOCIAL DEMANDS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the pedagogical foundations of shaping students' behavior based on social requirements. It sheds light on the role of moral education, social norms and values in personal development from a scientific and theoretical perspective. It also discusses the effectiveness of pedagogical tools, methods and forms of influence in regulating students' behavior in the educational process.

Entrance

In modern society, the issue of comprehensively educating the younger generation is of urgent importance. In particular, the formation of students' behavior based on social requirements is one of the priority tasks of today's education system. Because the worthy place of a person in society, his social activity and attitude to life largely depend on the behavioral norms formed in childhood and adolescence. The behavior of students develops not only under the influence of their individual characteristics, but also under the influence of the social environment surrounding them, family upbringing and the education system. Therefore, the formation of behavior taking into account social requirements in the pedagogical process is of great scientific and practical importance. The role of the teacher in this process is of particular importance, he acts not only as a giver of knowledge, but also as an educator. In today's globalization, while various cultural and informational influences are intensifying, the need to form strong moral immunity in students is increasing. From this perspective, the development of their behavior based on social norms is recognized as one of the important areas of pedagogical science. This article analyzes the pedagogical foundations of this issue from a scientific and theoretical perspective.

Main part

The formation of students' behavior based on social requirements is one of the important directions of pedagogical science. This process is manifested as one of the main factors in the adaptation of a person to society, active participation in social relations, and spiritual and moral maturity. Therefore, the issue of forming students' behavior requires special attention not only theoretically, but also practically.

The concept of behavior refers to a system of actions that express a person's attitude to the environment, society and other people. It includes a person's moral views, values, habits and attitude to social norms. The behavior of students is especially variable and is closely related to their age characteristics, psychological state and social experience. Therefore, the

formation of behavior in the pedagogical process should be carried out consistently, systematically and goal-oriented. Social requirements, on the other hand, are a set of moral norms, rules and values accepted by society. Through them, society regulates the behavior of its members and ensures a certain social order. Educating students on the basis of these requirements accelerates the process of their socialization and helps them find their place in society. From this point of view, it is important that educational work carried out in educational institutions is organized in harmony with social requirements.

Pedagogically, the formation of behavior consists of several main components. First, it is the process of imparting knowledge. Students need to be given concepts of moral norms, social rules, and human values. In this case, explaining them through real-life examples, rather than being limited to theoretical knowledge, will give effective results. Second, it is the process of forming skills and competencies. Students should be educated on the basis of various exercises, role-playing games, and problem situations so that they can apply the knowledge they have acquired in practice. Third, it is the formation of motivation and internal needs. If a student perceives adherence to social norms as an internal need, his behavior will be more stable. Various pedagogical methods and tools are used to form the behavior of students in the educational process. In particular, methods such as explanation, example-setting, encouragement, and punishment are widely used. However, in modern pedagogical approaches, more positive incentives, person-centered learning, and methods based on cooperation are considered a priority. Because such approaches develop the student's independent thinking and strengthen his or her intrinsic motivation.

The teacher's personal example is also an important factor in shaping the behavior of students. Students often observe the behavior of adults and strive to follow their example. Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to demonstrate such qualities as moral purity, justice, responsibility and respect in his work. This directly affects the formation of positive behavioral qualities in students. Also, family and school cooperation plays an important role in this process. If a student can continue the education he received at school in the family, his behavior will develop more stably and consistently. Otherwise, as a result of various conflicting influences, the student may experience a state of hesitation. Therefore, regular communication with parents and involving them in the educational process are one of the important tasks.

Today, the rapid development of information technologies has a significant impact on the behavior of students. Students, who are exposed to various information through the Internet and social networks, do not always have sufficient experience in selectively accepting it. As a result, sometimes behavior that contradicts social norms can be observed. Therefore, educators should also pay special attention to the formation of information culture in students. This is done by developing their critical thinking and forming the skills to distinguish between useful and harmful information. The use of national values and cultural heritage is also of great importance in the process of forming students' behavior based on social requirements. Because each society educates the younger generation through its historical experience and cultural traditions. National values serve to form such qualities in students as patriotism, respect, tolerance and humanity. At the same time, it is an important task to harmonize these values with the requirements of modern education.

In general, the formation of student behavior is a multifactorial and complex process that requires a consistent approach. In this process, pedagogical influence, social environment, family, media and other factors are closely interconnected. Therefore, a comprehensive approach to this issue is necessary, and effective results can be achieved based on the cooperation of all educational subjects.

Conclusion

The formation of students' behavior based on social requirements is a complex but important pedagogical process. This process is manifested as one of the main factors determining not only the level of knowledge of a person, but also his moral views, social activity and place in society. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a systematic and purposeful approach to this issue in the education system.

The effectiveness of pedagogical influence in shaping the behavior of students largely depends on the correct interpretation of the content of social norms, their connection with practical activities, and the development of internal motivation in students. Of particular importance is the teacher's personal example, the creation of a positive environment, and a respectful approach to the student's personality. Also, the consistent establishment of cooperation between the family and the educational institution ensures the stable formation of student behavior. Because the educational process is not limited to school, but is carried out in close connection with the family and the wider social environment. Therefore, ensuring a unified approach and mutual understanding between all educational subjects is one of the important tasks. In modern conditions, the intensification of the flow of information and the increase in various external influences impose new requirements on student behavior. This requires educators to use not only traditional educational methods, but also to introduce innovative approaches. In particular, developing critical thinking, independent decision-making, and social responsibility in students is one of the urgent tasks of today.

In conclusion, the effectiveness of shaping students' behavior based on social requirements depends on a comprehensive approach, that is, a combination of pedagogical, social and psychological factors. By properly organizing this process, it is possible to educate a responsible, conscious and active person for society.

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